

U.S. ARMY COMBAT CAPABILITIES DEVELOPMENT COMMAND ARMY RESEARCH LABORATORY

**Influence of Fabric Architecture and Sizing on ILFT/LVI Property for
Improving Durability and Damage Tolerance of GFRP Composites**

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Influence of Fabric Architecture and Sizing on ILFT/LVI Property for Improving Durability and Damage Tolerance of GFRP Composites

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Composites in Protective Applications

Vehicle primary protective structure
Source: AGY 2009

Spall Liner
Source: AGY 2009

Helmets and body armor
Source: Crouch 2017

Components of multi-material armor systems
Source: Ma 2006

Design Goal	Attribute	Design Outcome
Durability	Resistance to Damage	High Delamination Resistance
Damage Tolerance	Retention of Functional Performance after Damage	High Retention of Original Stiffness after Impact Damage

Impact Damage Energy Absorption

Improving Energy Dissipation

Objective

Improve durability and damage tolerance GFRP

Improve durability and damage tolerance protective-structural parts against low velocity impact (LVI)

Role of fracture toughness

Understand the role of fracture toughness on the LVI performance

Role of fabric architecture

Understand the role of fabric architecture and nesting on fracture toughness and impact performance

Role of sizing and fiber/matrix interface

Understand the role of fiber/matrix interface on fracture toughness and impact performance

Material Systems: Resin Systems

SC-15 Epoxy (Baseline)

- Long standing baseline, being replaced due to issues with high temperature performance ($T_g = 85^\circ\text{C}$)
- Two part infusible toughened epoxy resin system

RDL-RDC Epoxy

- SC-15 replacement by Huntsman with superior high temperature performance ($T_g = 122^\circ\text{C}$)
- Similar to SC-15, an infusible two part toughened
- Similar or better mechanical strengths with S-2 Glass

The Army's wet T_g requirement requires a change in the matrix system

Material System: Fabric Architecture

S-2 Glass

- High strength aluminosilicate glass used for protective-structural applications in the US Army vehicles

Fabric Weave Architecture

- Coarse plain weave historically used for protective-structural
- A light weight 8-harness satin weave, approximately 37% areal weight of the plain weave

Sizing

- 463 sizing system historically used for this application
- 933 sizing marketed as a damage tolerant sizing system

814 g/m² Plain weave
8 plies for a 5 mm thick sample

305 g/m² 8-harness satin
20 plies for a 5 mm thick sample

Material System Combinations Evaluated

Sample Fabrication

System Combinations

	Plain Weave (24 oz/yd ²)	8-Harness Satin (9 oz/yd ²)
AGY 463 Sizing	SC-15 and RDL-RDC	N/A
AGY 933 Sizing	SC-15 and RDL-RDC	SC-15 and RDL-RDC

Evaluating Mode II Fracture Toughness

End Notched Flexure (ENF) Test

FIG. 2 ENF Specimen, Fixture, and Dimensions

$$G_{IIC}^{SH} = \frac{9P^2 a^2}{16E_f w^2 h^3} \left(1 + 0.2 \left(\frac{E_f}{G_{13}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \right)$$

ENF Testing

$$G_{IIC}^{SH} = \frac{9P^2 a^2}{16E_f w^2 h^3} \left(1 + 0.2 \left(\frac{E_f}{G_{13}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \right)$$

Effect of the Resin

PW(463) shows resin insensitivity, while RDL-RDC shows improved fracture toughness over SC-15 with 933 sizing; however, the plain weave architecture seems to be creating a larger spread in the data

Effect of the Fiber Sizing

SC-15 shows sizing insensitivity while RDL-RDC seems to show a modest increase in fracture toughness due to the sizing

Effect of the Fabric Architecture

The fabric architecture shows an increase in fracture toughness due to the nesting, requiring more energy to fracture

Higher Fracture Toughness vs Increasing Interfaces

24 oz/yd² PW

- Higher fracture toughness at larger crack lengths
- Mechanical interlocking of tows for increased energy absorption through

9 oz/yd² 8HS

- x2.7 more interlaminar interfaces to potentially fracture

24 oz/yd² Plain Weave (8 plies/5 mm)

9 oz/yd² 8-HS (20 plies/5 mm)

Low Velocity Impact Test

Initial Stiffness

- Bolts tighten to 75 lbf-in
- Loaded to 0.8 mm
- Subtract machine compliance

Impact Test (40 J)

- Mass: 13.7 kg
- Height: 0.3 m
- Velocity: 2.4 m/s
- Impactor Geometry: 12 mm hemispherical tip

Post Impact Stiffness

- Bolts tighten to 75 lbf-in
- Loaded to 0.8 mm
- Subtract machine compliance

LVI Impact Energy

- The force vs time and displacement show similar responses
- The absorbed energy shows RDL-RDC generally absorbs less energy, thus less damage is expected

LVI Damage and Property Retention

S-2 Glass/SC-15 LVI Samples Sectioned

- PW shows ~7 primary cracks
- Crack branching and tow cracking observed
- 8HS shows only nine interlaminar interface fractures (19 interfaces are present) and some back face damage due to tension failure

PW(463)/SC-15

PW(933)/SC-15

8HS(933)/SC-15

S-2 Glass/RDL-RDC LVI Samples Sectioned

PW(463)/RDL-RDC

PW(463)/RDL-RDC

PW(933)/RDL-RDC

PW(933)/RDL-RDC

8HS(933)/RDL-RDC

8HS(933)/RDL-RDC

Main Crack Measurements and Analysis

- Energy absorption from the primary crack only captures <50% of the absorbed energy
- The effects of tow cracking, crack branching, fiber breaking, strain rate effects, and other damage modes are unaccounted for

Key Findings on

Fracture Toughness

- Sizing alone shows a slight improvement in mode II fracture toughness for one of the epoxy systems
- The fabric architecture and mechanical interlocking due to fabric nesting show significant contributions to fracture toughness

Damage Tolerance and Durability

- Modest increases in fracture toughness show a reduction in damage
- Increasing interlaminar interfaces reduces the damage area more significantly than the increase in fracture toughness

Key Findings on

- Evaluation of the sectioned laminates shows that the main interlaminar cracks account for less than half of the energy absorbed; further evaluation is necessary to determine other sources of energy absorption
 - Tow cracking, crack branching, fiber breaking, etc
- 8HS(933)/RDL-RDC showed a 50% reduction in delamination diameter, indicating improvement in durability and more than 33% improvement in damage tolerance while meeting the wet T_g requirements previously not met by the PW(463)/SC-15 system

Path Forward

- Improved fracture area analysis needs to be developed for a better understanding of the damage extent
- The strain-rate effect on the fracture toughness of these systems needs to be understood to capture the fracture energy release rates better for an LVI event
- Fracture surface analysis to understand the damage mode and compare to the ENF testing to gain insights into some key differences in damage evolution and identify potential mechanisms not captured in ENF present in LVI experiments
- Incorporation of a compliant thermoplastic interlayer may be able to absorb and allow for the flexure during impact, preventing or restricting delamination and retaining higher property retention

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